

These templates form Annex 2 of 'Methodological Guidelines for WP4'

Please refer back to the guidance document for details relating to specific elements
<https://data.d4science.net/6kEk>

This version of the diagram template corresponds to **WP4 methodological guidance v6.2**

- Templates include a legend/key to the left of the slide, which allows box labels in the body of the slide to be removed – leaving more space for details relating to your VC
- Where you see the comments box click for more information regarding completion of the template
- Space has been provided at the bottom of the slide for abbreviations, allowing for more space in the body of the template where necessary

New templates have been added to support analysis of spatial aspects (slide 4) and assemblage (slide 5)

[PRODUCT] VALUE CHAIN

Date
Version
Authors

MRL NAME + country

LEGEND

Infrastructure

Connection to stage

Practices

FOCAL PRODUCT(S)

CONDUCTIVE ENABLING SETTING

FOCAL PRODUCT(S)

- ...

Comments relating to conducive enabling setting diagram

Key governance institutions

4 Sharon Flan... 15 December 2021 X

- For each example of governance institutions create a new box of the appropriate shape (using the legend) and indicate with arrows connections to the relevant stage(s)

- You don't need the institution label (e.g. 'finance') in the boxes in the diagram body, just the institution name.

- You may have multiple boxes of the same shape for key institutions you want to include in the diagram, or you may choose to list all relevant institutions of that type in the same box if the connections to practice stage(s) are the same.

Reply...

Key regional infrastructure

4 Sharon Flan... 15 December 2021 X

- For each example of regional infrastructure create a new box of the appropriate shape (using the legend) and indicate with arrows connections to the relevant stage(s)

- You don't need the infrastructure label (e.g. 'transport') in the boxes in the diagram body, just the infrastructure name.

- You may have multiple boxes of the same shape for key infrastructure you want to include in the diagram, or you may choose to list all relevant infrastructure of that type in the same box if the connections to practice stage(s) are the same.

Reply...

[PRODUCT] VALUE CHAIN

Date
Version
Authors

MRL NAME + country

LEGEND

- Economic value/outcome
- Socio-cultural value/outcome
- Environmental value/outcome

Mountain Reference Landscape (MRL) scale

Mountain Reference Region (MRR) scale

Member state/national scale

EU/international scale

SPATIAL ANALYSIS

FOCAL PRODUCT (S)

- ...

ABBREVIATIONS

• ...	• ...	• ...
• ...	• ...	• ...
• ...	• ...	• ...

Comments relating to spatial analysis diagram

SPATIAL ANALYSIS

Sharon Flanigan 12 January 2022

 The key purpose of this diagram is, to consider HOW YOUR FOCAL VC IS SITUATED IN SPACE; and to illustrate HOW AND WHERE VALUE AND OUTCOMES ARE GENERATED AND BENEFITS ARE REALISED.

Partners should adapt the spatial categories to reflect this and use the shapes to illustrate where VC elements sit in space.

-- For example, if all of the VC sits within the MRL (perhaps extending slightly into the MRR) the national and international areas may not be required (delete).

-- Another example may be where key capital inputs must be sourced from outside the MRL (e.g. grain for whisky coming from lowland regions) or where key actors are international players based on urban centres.

Partners may decide to use more than one spatial analysis diagram to represent different aspects of their VC narrative

--For example, representing where economic, socio-cultural, and environmental value/outcomes sit in space may necessitate a separate slide to represent an additional 'layer' of effects based on where key actors, practices, etc are situated.

Reply...

[PRODUCT] VALUE CHAIN

Date
Version
Authors

MRL NAME + country

LEGEND

Territorial capital (blue box with arrow)
Actors (purple box)
Practices (grey box)

FOCAL PRODUCT(S) (red box with arrow)
ADDITIONAL VC PRODUCT(S) (pink box with arrow)
Flows (yellow box)

Mountain Reference Landscape (MRL) scale (dotted line)

Economic (blue)
Socio-cultural (light blue)
Environmental (lightest blue)

Connection (& direction) (solid arrow)
Bi-directional connection (double-headed arrow)

ABBREVIATIONS

- ...
- ...
- ...

Comments relating to assemblage diagram

Sharon Flanigan 13 January 2022

The key purpose of this diagram is to illustrate KEY POINTS OF INTERACTION between the focal VC and additional VC within the MRL and HOW THE ASSEMBLAGE INFLUENCES OUTCOMES in the focal VC in the context of the MRL.

This will require strict definition of the boundaries of both VCs so that the connections can be identified.

Only basic details are required for the focal VC, including key aspects that connect it with the additional VC in the assemblage.

Partners may want to 'zoom in' on particular stages of the VC process in either or both chains (removing less important stages) to provide more detail.

Partners may also choose which elements are important to represent in the context of assemblage and only include those details.

Key points of interaction should be illustrated using arrows to indicate the direction of relationships

-- For example, by products in one VC may represent territorial capital inputs in the other.

-- Another example might be where key actors are involved in both VCs

Reply...